

Development of word formation regularities by learners of German as a foreign/second language

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Recognizing word formation regularities and using them to comprehend and create complex words is not a particular challenge for native speakers. This word formation competence is otherwise crucial for learners of German as a second language. Its importance has long been justified in the specialist literature (cf. Storch/Storch-Luche 1979, Thurmair 1997, Storch 2001, Simeckova 2004, Mac 2009, Gärtner 2012) primarily by the economic possibility of vocabulary expansion. However, acquiring the competence of word formation is impeded by the multitude and complexity of word formation rules, as well as the numerous irregularities and polyfunctionalities of the German word formation. Furthermore, the lack of sufficient qualitative and quantitative data from learner language research hinders the establishment of a systematic word formation didactic.

Previous studies on word formation in learner languages represent exclusively cross-sectional studies. Berth 2009, Zeldes 2013 and Coca 2021 showed, based on the corpora of the Falko family, a significant underuse of the investigated word formation patterns, although advanced learners of German as a second language can usually recognize and use them productively.

The question of the development of such word formation regularities remains unanswered due to the data basis of the corpora studied thus far. However, it is of great importance especially regarding the resulting implications for the didactics of German as a second language. Within the framework of a pseudo-longitudinal study, this development will be outlined on the basis of the most productive native adjective-forming suffixes of German.

As a corpus basis, texts from the "Written Text Production" section of the DSH examination (Deutschen Sprachprüfung für den Hochschulzugang) were used. Three subcorpora were created from a complete semester data set of the Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg (FAU), based on the three DSH levels. The primary objective of the project is to enable an investigation of the development of the word formation competence of the learners.

The analysis includes quantitative and qualitative aspects. Contrastive Interlanguage Analysis (CIA) is used to compare the productive use of the investigated suffixes at individual developmental levels. Computer-Aided Error Analysis (CEA) is used to examine error types in the developmental levels, capturing the qualitative development of word formation

competence in the adjective domain. The compilation and annotation of a learner corpus presents a particular challenge.

References

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